

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7330946>

UDK 616.891

DEPENDENCE OF THE ADAPTIVE POTENTIAL OF MEDICAL STUDENTS ON THE INDIVIDUAL LEVEL OF STRESS RESISTANCE AND WEATHER SENSITIVITY

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Annotation: The influence of stress levels and weather sensitivity on the adaptive potential of medical students has been studied. As a result of the study, it was revealed that the majority of medical students have an unsatisfactory assessment of the adaptive potential, which has a significant impact on the further development of the level of stress resistance and the presence of weather sensitivity. This indicates that the last two indicators are inversely proportional to the first one: the lower the index of adaptive material, the higher the level of stress resistance and the presence of weather sensitivity in respondents.

Keywords: stress, weather sensitivity, adaptive potential

ЗАВИСИМОСТЬ АДАПТАЦИОННОГО ПОТЕНЦИАЛА СТУДЕНТОВ-МЕДИКОВ ОТ ИНДИВИДУАЛЬНОГО УРОВНЯ СТРЕССОУСТОЙЧИВОСТИ И МЕТЕОЧУВСТВИТЕЛЬНОСТИ

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Аннотация: Изучено влияние уровня стресса и метеочувствительности на адаптационный потенциал студентов-медиков. В результате исследования выявлено, что у большинства студентов-медиков наблюдается неудовлетворительная оценка адаптационного потенциала, что имеет весомое влияние на дальнейшее развитие уровня стрессоустойчивости и наличия метеочувствительности. Это свидетельствует о том, что два последних показателя находятся в обратно пропорциональной зависимости от первого: чем ниже показатель адаптационного материала, тем выше уровень стрессоустойчивости и наличие метеочувствительности у респондентов.

Keywords: стресс, метеочувствительность, адаптационный потенциал

Relevance. Today the world is experiencing global changes in society, which requires a high level of adaptive potential from the individual himself in order to be successful in his personal and professional development [1-3].

I.P. Pavlov and I.M. Sechenov consider adaptation as an organism's reaction aimed at maintaining its vital activity in a constantly changing external environment. In other words, adaptation is the process and result of human interaction with the environment, the body's response to the impact of any factors on the human body. I.e. from the perspective of this

view, the adaptive potential is the reserve internal forces of the body that regulate the human response to external environmental factors, forming an adequate response of the body to the surrounding reality [4].

It is also important to note that meteosensitivity is defined as the ability of an organism to respond with a physiological compensatory or, in case of violation of adaptive mechanisms, a pathological reaction to the action of adverse weather factors. Increased meteosensitivity is a reduced resistance of the body to changing meteorological conditions, which, as a rule, is accompanied by the development of pathological metotropic (meteopathic) reactions. The ability to react to the weather manifests itself from birth as an evolutionarily mandatory program of the functioning of the body associated with protection from environmental factors [1, 7].

At the same time, stress resistance is a complex systemic characteristic of a person, which reflects his ability to successfully carry out his activities in difficult and extreme conditions [6, 8].

It also turned out that the characteristic of the negative impact of meteorological and geophysical changes is a disadaptive reaction of the body, manifested in the form of increasing meteorological sensitivity, accompanied by a decrease in mood, the occurrence of negative emotional manifestations (insomnia or hypersomnia, depression, fear, aggression), deterioration of well-being, the appearance of weakness, headache, increased or decreased blood pressure, decreased appetite, the appearance of vegetative imbalance, hypertensive crises, angina attacks and other exacerbations of chronic diseases [2].

Stress-induced diseases are based on prolonged and (or) intense excitation of the adrenergic and pituitary-adrenal systems, which is associated with an increase in catecholamines and glucocorticoids in the blood, primarily, as well as an imbalance of other hormones: STH, thyroid, insulin and glucagon, activation of the renin-angiotensin-aldosterone system [5, 7, 8].

The purpose of the work: to study the influence of stress levels and weather sensitivity on the adaptive potential of medical students

Materials and methods of research. The valeological and diagnostic study was conducted among 98 respondents (14.1 % of them male, 85.9 % female) studying at the Grodno State Medical University aged 18 to 25 years. The survey of respondents was conducted on the Internet using assessment tests of the level of adaptive potential, weather

sensitivity and stress resistance uploaded to the Google forms platform. Inclusion criteria: informed consent. The results were processed using the Google forms Platform.

Results. According to the results of the study, a satisfactory assessment of the adaptive potential is present in 19.39 % of respondents. The stress of adaptation mechanisms was revealed in 36.73 % of the respondents, 83.33 % of them have an average stress level, 11.1% have a high stress level, 36.11 % have weather sensitivity. 36.73 % of respondents have an unsatisfactory assessment of adaptive potential, of which 75 % have an average level of stress, 16.7 % have a high level of stress, 80.55% have meteorological sensitivity, hypermeteosensitivity – 2.7 %. Adaptation failure is observed in 7.14 % of those who have passed the test, 71.5 % of them have an average level of stress, 28.5 % have a high level of stress. Meteosensitivity affects 28.5 % of participants in the trial with a breakdown of adaptation, 14.3 % suffer from hypermeteosensitivity.

Conclusions. Summing up, it should be noted that the majority of medical students have an unsatisfactory assessment of adaptive potential, which has a significant impact on the further development of the level of stress resistance and the presence of weather sensitivity. This suggests that the last two indicators are inversely proportional to the first: the lower the index of adaptive material, the higher the level of stress resistance and the presence of weather sensitivity in respondents.

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Поступила в редакцию 18.10.2021

Принята к публикации 01.11.2022

Для цитирования:

Zimatkina T.I., Aleksandrovich A.S., Novak I.U. Dependence of the adaptive potential of medical students on the individual level of stress resistance and weather sensitivity // Инновационные научные исследования. 2022. № 11-1(23). С. 23-28. URL: <https://ip-journal.ru/>